

Qualitative Preregistration

Metadata

Title*

Evaluation of a Peer Mentoring scheme to support interdisciplinary skills development and collaborations for post-doctoral researchers in Biomedical Data Science

Description*

As technical capabilities advance and data volumes increase, so does the need for collaborative interdisciplinary science. However, working across different disciplinary boundaries can be challenging due to misaligned expectations, discipline-specific technical language and misguided assumptions. These challenges affect all of those who work in research environments, but can be particularly felt by those at the post-doctoral level who feel increasing pressure to establish themselves as independent researchers in a competitive academic landscape.

To tackle these issues, we have developed a peer mentoring programme designed to bring together post-doctoral level researchers across either computational or non-computational disciplines within biomedical research. We aimed to develop a programme that would create a non-judgmental environment where researchers felt able to ask basic questions from those in other fields, while also allowing space for post-doctoral researchers to reflect on their own career journey and development with their peers.

In this qualitative study, we will use a mixed method approach of workshops and surveys embedded throughout the scheme to determine how well this activity was able to support:

- Interdisciplinary communication skills
- Networking and community building
- Navigation of career paths and development

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Contributors*

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Life Sciences

Medicine and Health Sciences

Bioinformatics

Translational Medical research

Tags

Health Data Science

Biomedical data science

Biomedical research data

Interdisciplinary science

Team science biomedical

Team science Health

Study Information

Research Aims*

Please specify the overall purposes, objectives or aims of the research.

If relevant, please reflect on whether your aim is different across different domains (e.g. knowledge generation, policy development, community resourcing). If so, specify your aim for each domain that is relevant for your study.

The overall aim of this study is to evaluate whether peer mentoring across different disciplines is effective in developing interdisciplinary communication skills, network building and career confidence among post-doctoral researchers in biomedical science.

If helpful, please select the type of aim (non-exhaustive list):

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- Exploring
- Describing
- Theory evaluating
- Comparing
- Understanding

Research question(s)*

Please specify your research question or questions as they are guiding your research now. If relevant, you may also specify here any hypotheses to be assessed. The research questions may break down your aim into smaller, distinct inquiries.

If relevant, you may distinguish between primary and secondary research questions or hypotheses.

Example: If it is your aim to explore the attitudes of caregivers towards Alzheimer patients in a local ward, your research questions could specify precisely what you plan to study; for instance, how ward staff tries to treat the patients with dignity or how the relationship between the patient and their family members or loved ones evolved since that patient was admitted to the ward.

RQ: Is peer mentoring an effective way to support interdisciplinary skills development for biomedical scientists?

- SUB-RQ1: Does peer mentoring improve confidence around speaking to those from other disciplines?
- SUB-RQ2: Is peer mentoring effective in building interdisciplinary networks and reducing silos?
- SUB-RQ3: How can peer mentoring schemes be developed to best support the career development needs of post-doctoral researchers
- SUB-RQ4: Are there any benefits of peer mentoring that were unexpected?

Anticipated Duration *

Please indicate the estimated project start date (mm/yyyy) and estimated project end date (mm/yyyy).

6th Jan 2026 – 31st March 2027

Design Plan

Study design *

Please provide a brief, overarching characterisation of the study design.

Your response might consist of a succinct label (e.g., “case study” or “ethnography”) and/or a brief elaboration of that label’s meaning.

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A study may involve a combination of different designs, including a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods.

The study has been designed to evaluate the scheme using a mixed methods approach (surveys and focus groups/workshops) which are embedded into the scheme design.

Sampling and case selection strategy *

Please describe your sampling or recruitment strategy (examples include, but are not limited to: purposive, snowball, theoretical, and maximum variation sampling) and/or your case selection strategy (examples include, but are not limited to: typical case, most similar case, most different case, diverse case, and deviant case).

Please provide a short rationale for why you selected this type of strategy.

To achieve our aim of creating a UK-wide network of post-doctoral researchers with a diverse range of experiences, we did not want to limit our recruitment to one specific network. Our recruitment strategy will focus on non-targeted distribution through mailing lists known to include both computational and non-computational researchers. Examples include: Medical Research Council (MRC) units, institutes and Centres of Research Excellence, scientific societies and existing national research networks relevant to biomedical research, and institutes of our collaborating partners across the Biomedical Data Science Leadership Awards.

We limited our remit to only include post-doctoral level researchers within UK-based academic research institutions. This allows us to ensure all participants feel they share some 'common ground' and to encourage open communication without hierarchy. However, within this remit, we sought to include researchers from a diverse range of academic institutions, and across a range of disciplines and fields within biomedical science. For example, we sought to include those from purely computational roles as well as purely laboratory-based roles, and to encourage applications from a variety of subject/disease interests.

Participants will be selected to ensure balanced representation of those from computational and non-computational domains, and representation of a diverse number of institutions throughout the UK. Where there is an over-abundance of applicants, priority will be given to those who's applications suggested they may benefit most from participating in this scheme. This includes those with lower baseline confidence scores, those whose biographies align best with the scheme aims, and those at a later career stage who may not be eligible for many other career development opportunities. Those who apply earlier will be given priority to ensure the scheme has enough participants to go ahead, and to give time to contact additional participants as needed.

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Data Collection

Data source(s) and data type(s) *

Please describe the type(s) of data you will be using. In describing the data, distinguish between data that existed prior to your study (e.g. archival documents, newspaper articles, [social] media, secondary literature, or data collected for a different purpose than the current study) and original data (i.e. data that will be collected/generated for the current study).

Data will be collected exclusively from primary sources. Data will be collected from post-doctoral researchers working across different disciplines in biomedical research.

Data collection methods *

Please describe your method of data collection or data generation. Examples of methods include (but are not restricted to) interviews, focus groups, enabling techniques, self-reports, field notes, diaries, (participative) observation, archival research, or mixed methods. Please provide a brief rationale for why you plan to use this particular data collection/generation method in your study.

1) Surveys

Surveys will be used to collect both qualitative and quantitative data, and will be embedded throughout the scheme to reduce additional workload for our scheme participants. Our recruitment survey will collect quantitative information around confidence that will serve as a baseline for subsequent evaluations. These questions will be repeated at scheme end (6 months) and post scheme (3 months after scheme end) to track confidence longitudinally. Surveys will also include qualitative questions to track unexpected outcomes and scheme feedback.

2) Focus groups/Workshops

Focus groups will be embedded into workshops at mid scheme (3 month) and end of scheme (6 month). Each workshop will focus on the following topics: Feedback on scheme design and initial impressions (3 months into the scheme), and overall scheme feedback (End of Scheme).

Each workshop will last between 90-120 minutes. The first 30 minutes of the workshop will be a talk from an invited speaker to allow participants to explore a specific aspect of career development, such as strategies for working in interdisciplinary teams, or how to network effectively. This will be followed by a 1-1.5 hour workshop session in which the group is invited to share their thoughts. The structure of this session will be guided by a topic guide covering 5-7 open-ended questions around an appropriate theme. Mentimeter will be used to allow the group to submit anonymous responses that can then be used to prompt more open discussion among the group. As our participants will be geographically dispersed across the UK, we will conduct all workshops online via MS Teams to

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facilitate maximum engagement. Participants will also be able to engage with questions using the chat function to help with accessibility.

Only workshops and surveys will be used to form our evaluation data. All mentoring conversations between matched groups will be fully confidential between mentees with no involvement from the mentoring coordinators and will not be recorded.

Data collection tools, instruments or plans *

Please describe or upload the tools, instruments or plans you will use in collecting or generating your data. Examples could be (but are not limited to): topic guide, interview questionnaire, focus group guide, observation scheme, creative tools (e.g. photos, videos, musical pieces, paintings, etc.), or a description of your archival search plans.

Before the beginning of the scheme, all participants will be asked to agree to a Code of Conduct which will outline expected behaviours throughout the programme. This is to enable a generation of a psychologically safe space within the cohort, and to ensure all participants know how to report any issues or access additional support. It will be made clear that participants should not share any information given to them within mentoring meetings with any party outside of their group unless express permission has been given by the individual.

Data will be collected using MS Forms for survey-based data, and MS Teams for workshops. The recording function for MS teams will be utilized to ensure the feedback captured is recorded accurately, but will only be used for accurate transcription purposes. Mentimeter will be used to allow participants to submit anonymous responses in workshops and this data will be used in output generation.

Before participation in the scheme and associated workshops, participants were provided with an information sheet outlining the research objectives and scheme activities, and specifying how the collected data will be used, stored, retained, and shared. Written consent must be obtained from all participants prior to taking part in scheme evaluations.

Stopping criteria *

Please describe the criteria or rationale behind when you will stop data generation or collection. Possible criteria include (but are not restricted to): data saturation*, when inclusion criteria are

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satisfied, resource constraints (e.g. time/funding), or when the analysis has produced an enriching answer to the research question(s).

Example: We follow Fusch & Ness (2005) and interpret saturation to be reached when there is enough information to replicate the study, the ability to obtain new information has been attained, and further coding is no longer feasible.

Recruitment places on the scheme were limited to 30 participants to allow for sufficient variation in participant expertise and institutions, while remaining a practical number of groups to follow up with throughout the scheme. Due to timing and funding constraints, our mentoring scheme was limited to a 6 month duration to allow time within the project to follow up on participants after the scheme end. However, 6-12 months is a typical duration of many existing mentoring schemes.

Analysis Plan

Data analysis approach *

Please specify the type and details of your data analysis approach. Examples of approaches include (but are not limited to): narrative analysis, phenomenological analysis, thematic analysis, content analysis, psychoanalytic analysis, grounded theory, process tracing, comparative analysis, or discourse analysis. If multiple interpretations of your approach exist, please specify the version you will be using. Please provide a rationale for why your selected data analytic approach is appropriate given your study's aim(s).

Example: If you indicated 'phenomenological analysis', you may want to specify the theorist whose approach you are following, e.g. "We use a phenomenological approach as explained by Colaizzi (1978)"; or if you indicated 'content analysis', a specification could be: "We apply inductive content analysis as described in Elo & Kyngäs (2008)".

In this study, we will apply thematic analysis, as described by Braun and Clarke (2006), to qualitative data obtained from longitudinal surveys and workshops embedded throughout the scheme. Thematic analysis was chosen to allow us to perform a nuanced analysis while identifying trends that may be more broadly generalizable. As a mixed methods approach will be used, we will triangulate across sources to enhance the credibility of findings.

Although we will be following a thematic analysis approach overall, we may also apply some narrative thinking to our analysis to show how specific themes develop over time for individuals.

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Data analysis process *

Please describe what your process of data analysis will look like. Questions to keep in mind could be (but are not limited to):

- * who will be involved in the data analysis, and in what role?
- * if relevant, indicate any procedures that will be used to turn “raw” data into analyzable form (e.g., a coding scheme)
- * if relevant, indicate any evidentiary criteria that will be used to assess any hypotheses (e.g., what evidence will count as consistent or inconsistent with a given proposition)
- * if relevant, what software or analytic tools will you use and how will you use them?

We will apply an inductive approach to our thematic analysis to allow relevant themes to emerge over time, rather than beginning with a set hypothesis. To identify these themes, coding will be performed on the raw data by two researchers (CG and RE) following the 6-step process outlined by Naeem et al. (2023)

The key analysis steps are described below:

- 1) **Selection of quotations:** Text from workshop transcripts or survey free text responses will be deidentified and quotations will be selected for analysis.
- 2) **Keywords:** The data will be analysed carefully to pick out patterns and recurring themes within the data. From this, we will identify a set of keywords which can be used as a bridge between raw data and initial codes.
- 3) **Coding:** After identifying keywords which reflect specific themes, we will distill sections of the text into ‘codes’, which are words or short phrases which indicate the underlying meaning of the data excerpt.
- 4) **Themes:** Themes are identified by grouping similar codes together to help identify broad themes across the data set.
- 5) **Conceptualisation:** Themes, codes and keywords identified from the data will be used to synthesis key concepts which may be broadly applicable in a wider context.
- 6) **Development of a conceptual model:** We will develop our findings into a narrative report which addresses the research questions and outlines the contributions of the study to the wider field.

Data sources for qualitative analysis will likely be analysed using qualitative data analysis computer software e.g. NVivo.

We will also use confidence scores collected during baseline, mid-stage and post- scheme surveys to provide a quantitative measure of interdisciplinary skills confidence over the course of the programme. This information will be anonymised before reporting to protect the individual identities of participants, and taken in the context of additional qualitative data to provide an accurate narrative.

Credibility strategies *

Please specify the strategies, actions or measures you will employ to assure methodological integrity. Examples include (but are not limited to):

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- Member checking
- **Triangulation with other data sources**
- Bringing in different perspectives
- **Have different researchers analyse the data**
- Consensus building among team members or 'interrater reliability'
- Negative case analysis
- Peer debriefing
- Cross-checks for rivaling explanations
- Bring in an 'auditor'
- **Reflexivity**
- Verisimilitude
- Emotionality
- Personal Responsibility
- An ethic of caring
- Political praxis
- Multivoiced texts
- **Dialogues with subjects**
- Other (please explain)

Please provide a short rationale for why you selected particular strategies and how they are appropriate given your study's aim(s) and approach, or specify your credibility strategies if not on the above list. *

As a credibility strategy, we will triangulate our findings across the different methods of data collection (surveys and focus groups) to ensure continuity of experiences. We will also compare our findings to that or related studies that have also evaluated the impact of mentoring schemes.

Themes will also be identified by two researchers to ensure that all relevant themes have been identified. As researchers, we will also reflect on our own biases and positionality when analysing the data.

To ensure that any quotations used in reporting are reflective of the participant's intentions, we will confirm that our participants are happy with us using their quotations in specific contexts before publishing them, as outlined in our attached consent document.

Miscellaneous

Reflection on your positionality

Feel free to reflect on your relation to or association with the studied phenomenon and your position in the research setting/field, including your academic/personal standpoints, assumptions and values.

In addition, if there is a potential conflict of interest [whether you have a previous relationship with the studied phenomenon, and if you consider that there are previous positions or

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assumptions that may influence the present study] that can arise, you may want to report that here.

Example: If you study the lives of detained immigrants, you might want to talk about your political viewpoints, experience working with detained immigrants, relevant policy work, or perhaps your own experience as a detained immigrant.

Reflection on positionality:

This research is part of the INTEGRATE project funded by the Medical Research Council and delivered in partnership between the University of Oxford, Health Data Research UK (HDR-UK), The University of Dundee and the Cancer Research UK (CRUK) Data Community Support Unit (2024-2027).

The authors of this research are white men and women employed at mid to senior career stages and bring a range of disciplinary perspectives and skills to the project. Of note, the researchers involved in this study have lived experience as bench-based and computational post-doctoral researchers within biomedical research. We share a strong commitment to equality, diversity and inclusion within our team, which is supported by inclusive institutional policies and practices, and many of our project team have been previously involved in related initiatives to improve interdisciplinarity and team science within research environments.

We acknowledge that the INTEGRATE project team lacks representation in terms of ethnicity, and that there is potential for blind spots within our methodology and outcomes. To address this, we have engaged in wider consultation with the community outside of our project team, including local EDI advisors within our institutions, and are actively engaging in a cross-award EDI working group as part of the Medical Research Council Biomedical Data Science Leadership Award group to help embed best practice into our recommendations.

No conflicts of interest have been identified in relation to this research.